

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

O. Otaxov

PAXTANI ARRACHALI BARABANGA ILDIRISH

MOSLAMASINI AMALIY O'RGANISH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2022/OKTABR

